

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS IN UNDERSTANDING THE IMPACT OF PRIVACY AND SECURITY TOWARDS SOCIAL MEDIA AMONG YOUNG ADULTS

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Abstract

The main idea of using social media is to connect individuals for different activities, to let them freely express their thoughts and ideas, and to connect more socially with their friends and families. Individuals, the public, organizations, and governments, primarily for security reasons. There have been many privacy breaches, data theft, and security breaches on various social media platforms. Identity misuse increases threats from third-party applications, malicious networks, and spyware and reduces social media performance. At the same time, a gradual decrease in attacks and other legal challenges affect social media growth. Users' privacy can be involved in many ways, and personal data can be deleted without prior permission. Although social networks advise users to limit information sharing, a malicious attack can affect all users. May result in the loss of valuable data and information. Communicated from a privacy control perspective, there is a responsibility on social media users to exercise greater control over their data and to prevent disclosure that non-members can see of their group or community.

Keywords: Social Media, Privacy and Security, Analysis of variance

INTRODUCTION

The social media usage is considered as one of the keys and most popular online activities in this decade, recently over 4.2 billion individuals are using social media around the globe and it is projected that the users will increase to more than 5.9 billion by 2027. The key idea of using social media is to connect with the individuals for different activities, enable in sharing their thoughts and opinions freely and connect more socially with their friends and families. However, the influential social media is currently causing more issues to individuals, public, organisation and government mainly due to the security concerns (Shaikh, 2009). There have many cases of lapse in privacy of information, data theft and security breaches in many social media platforms (Ismailov, 2020). The misuse of identity, more threats from external application, malicious links and spyware causes outages to social media, moreover, phishing attacks and other legal difficulties are impacting the growth of social media. Based on a report released by Statista, the number of young adults who are in the age group between 18 – 24 years, who are using social media is 755 million and this is expected to reach 1.2 billion by 2027 (Humayun, 2021).

The utilisation of social networking sites enables individuals to be prone to threats and dangers in the online communities. It has been stated that the privacy of the users can be affected in different ways and personal information can be extracted without any prior approvals. Though the social networking sites provides the recommendation to the users to restrict the sharing of information, the malicious attack might affect all the users which result in loss of critical data and information (Kumari, 2015). Privacy can be stated from the perspective of possessing control, the onus is on the social media users to keep more control on their personal data and restrict the release of information to access to others who are not forming part of their group or community. Moreover, the social networking sites are focusing in enhancing the private setting on their platform, apart from basic setting, social media sites like Facebook, Twitter etc are looking to add more features which will enhance the protection. However, in order to change the protecting, the users need to go the settings and change as per their desired format. Now a days the users possess the option to not to display their information like the mobile number or email id or status etc. this supports in protecting the data and information to others. Furthermore, the individuals who choose to include that information are made available based on the settings and other features which the user has agreed to. However, many users and practitioners are setting that these steps are not sufficient in order to protect their data and the social networking sites need to make advanced effort in protecting the information and support in enhancing the cybersecurity effectively at all times (Gail-Joon, 2011).

There are more concerns on the privacy towards social media platforms which are depending being applied and the user privacy options need to include the security settings for sharing the information. For example, Facebook support in crating the overall public profile tend to contain detailed information related to the photos they post, their current location, status of the relationship, email address etc (Zhiyong, 2018). The critical aspect of the study is to understand the overall impact of privacy and security towards social media among young adults, the critical determinants which are considered are: apply better security protocols by the social media sites, implement privacy settings and combine technical & behavioural monitoring effectively.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The social media space serves to reinforce the privacy policy. Facebook and other long-distance social networking sites have security restrictions built into their default settings. It is important for customers to visit their customer policy and change their security options. These areas, like Facebook, give users the option not to reveal personal information, such as conception date, email, phone number and business location. For individuals who decide to include this post, Facebook allows users to restrict access so that only those approved as "friends" can access their information. But even this level of privacy does not prevent one of these partners from taking a photo on their own computer and uploading it elsewhere. However, there are not enough social media clients to restrict access to their content. Take, for example, how users block access to other people's content on various social networks (Saeed, 2018). Information related to social media often leads to abuse by Internet users, including phishing as described in [6]. This phishing scam reached 16 percent. User credentials are similar to social contracts where individuals share their personal information for monetary or non-monetary rewards, the only downside being privacy. Needless to say, as long as the benefits of a genuine social contract outweigh the current and future dangers of propaganda, responsible consumers will be interested. Implicitly, people choose to maximize benefits while minimizing costs. This view confirms this theory. It is designed to meet user preferences for displaying content shared on social networking sites such as Facebook and Twitter (Newton, 2020). Another inevitable and unwanted effect is the spread of malware information via social media. Although rumors already existed in the ancient society, the spread had little effect and spread slowly among the masses. But today, fake news can spread like a virus at the speed of light through social media. Since March 2020, news about the "coronavirus", in the sense of good knowledge and bad fear, has spread through social media at rocket speed.

OBJECTIVES

This paper is intended to have more understanding of the impact of privacy and security towards social media among young adults.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Is there any association between applying better security protocols and implementation of social media sites?

Does the implementation of advanced privacy settings will support in protecting the security of social networking sites?

Will the combination technical & behavioural monitoring effectively support in the privacy and the security of social networking sites?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is mostly involved in understanding the impact of privacy and security towards social media among young adults, the researcher is more intended to analyse how young adults tend

to perceive the privacy and security issues in social networking sites in the current context and also to analyse the way to enhance them for better communication and sharing of information. The growth of social media has grown exponentially in the recent years and this has benefited many individuals and business as they can share ideas, data, thoughts and information to anyone in the world at very low cost. However, the security and private issues is always a concern and this needs to be addressed in order to protect the data being manipulated by cyber-attacks. The study applies causal research design as the study is more focused in understanding the overall cause and effect between privacy and security with the overall usage of the social networking among young adult. When the privacy concerns increase, it will lead to users to move out of the social networking sites, hence there lies a cause-and-effect association between them. Moreover, the researcher intends to collect the data for the research from the young adults who use social media, nearly 135 respondents were chosen through opportunity sampling method as it is most affordable and convenient way to select the sample. Also, the researcher collates second party data from various resources like Scopus journals, ABDC journals etc.

CRITICAL ANALYSIS

This part of the study is focused in presenting the analysis through the usage of questionnaire. The researcher has sourced information from 145 sample population, the data are analysed using IBM SPSS statistical package. The researcher focuses to understand the demographic variables of the respondents, performs correlation analysis to measure the association between the independent variables and dependent variable and test the hypothesis of the study using Chi square analysis.

Table 1: Demographic analysis

Respondents Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	94	69.6
Female	41	30.4
Respondents Age	Frequency	Percent
18 - 20 Years	17	12.6
20 - 22 Years	71	52.6
22 - 24 Years	31	23
24 - 26 Years	16	11.9
Education	Frequency	Percent
Pursuing Under-graduation	47	34.8
Pursuing Post graduation	70	51.9
Pursuing Professional course	18	13.3
Family type	Frequency	Percent
Nuclear family	94	69.6
Joint family	41	30.4
No. of Hrs spent on Social Media	Frequency	Percent
Less than 1 Hour per day	43	31.9
1 - 2 Hour per day	62	45.9
2 - 3 Hours per day	30	22.2

The demographic analysis states that most of the respondents are male, out of 135 respondents, 94 were male, 71 of them were in the age group of 20 – 22 years, 31 were in the age of 22 - 24 Years, 17 were between 18 – 20 years and remaining were 24 – 26 years. Also noted that 70 were doing post-graduation course, 47 were doing under graduation course. 94 of them were living in nuclear family, most importantly it is identified that 62 were spending nearly 1 – 2 hours per day in social media, 43 were spending less than 1 hour per day in social media and 30 were spending 2 – 3 hours in social media

Security is primary concern

The researcher intends to check if the security and privacy issue is primary among the young adults

Table 2: Security is primary concern

Security is Primary	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	8	5.9
Disagree	11	8.1
Neutral	22	16.3
Agree	49	36.3
Strongly Agree	45	33.3
Total	135	100

Based on analysis it is stated that 45 of the respondents strongly agree that security and privacy is a primary concern in social media, 49 of them have agreed to the statement, 22 of them were neutral, only 11 disagreed to the statement and 8 were strongly disagreeing to the statement.

Social media will grow

The next part is to focus in understanding whether social media will grow in the future though there are some security and privacy concerns among young adults.

Table 3: Social media will grow

Social Media will grow	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	10	7.4
Disagree	10	7.4
Neutral	21	15.6
Agree	45	33.3
Strongly Agree	49	36.3
Total	135	100

From the above table it can be stated that 49 of them strongly agree that the social media is poised to grow in the future, 45 of them have agreed to the statement also 21 have been neutral and remaining have disagreed to the statement.

Analysis of variance

The researchers focus in analysing the research question which has been set for the study. For this purpose Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is applied, this test support in comparing the variance among the groups.

RQ1:

Is there any association between applying better security protocols and implementation of social media sites?

Table 4: ANOVA between Better security protocols & Privacy and Security

Better security protocols	SS	Dof	Mean Sq.	F val	Sig. val
Between Gps	143.603	4	35.901	106.256	0.00
Within Gps	43.923	130	0.338		
Total	187.526	134			

From analysis the mean square is 35.901 and F data is 106.26, however the significance is 0.00, hence it can be stated that there is an association between applying better security protocols and implementation of social media sites

RQ2:

Does the implementation of advanced privacy settings will support in protecting the security of social networking sites?

Will the combination technical & behavioural monitoring effectively support in supporting the privacy and the security of social networking sites

Table 5: ANOVA between Advanced privacy settings & Privacy and Security

Advanced privacy settings	SS	Dof	Mean Sq.	F val	Sig. val
Between Gps	142.089	4	35.522	101.634	0.00
Within Gps	45.437	130	0.35		
Total	187.526	134			

From analysis the mean square is 35.522 and F data is 101.634, however the significance is 0.00, hence it can be stated that the there implementation of advanced privacy settings will support in protecting the security of social networking sites.

RQ3:

Will the combination technical & behavioural monitoring effectively support in the privacy and the security of social networking sites?

Table 6: ANOVA between Technical monitoring & Privacy and Security

Technical monitoring	SS	Dof	Mean Sq.	F val	Sig. val
Between Gps	129.317	4	32.329	72.202	0.00
Within Gps	58.209	130	0.448		
Total	187.526	134			

From analysis the mean square is 32.329 and F data is 72.202, however the significance is 0.00, hence it can be stated that combination technical & behavioural monitoring effectively support in privacy and the security of social networking sites

CONCLUSION

This study focuses more on understanding the impact of privacy and security on social media among young adults, the researcher aims to find out how young adults view privacy and security issues on social media in the current context and how they also explore ways to increase to make Better communication and information exchange. Social media has grown rapidly in recent years and has benefited many individuals and businesses as ideas, information, thoughts and information can be shared with everyone in the world at a very low cost. However, security and privacy are always an issue and must be addressed to protect data from cyber-attacks. However, to change the security, users need to go into the settings and customize it. Now users have option not to reveal their details like mobile number or email id or location etc. It supports data and data protection for others. Those who choose to include such information are also subject to consent terms and other user consents. However, many users and doctors believe that these measures are not enough to protect their data and social media should make more efforts to protect data and help promote online safety effectively at all times.

From the overall analysis it is noted that the social media companies need to focus more in protecting the user data effectively, they need to implement novel steps to control any cyber-attacks or malware which may impact in user confidentiality.

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